

European Research Council
Executive Agency

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HealthXCross

ERC Data Management Plan

European Research Council

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Project Acronym	Project Number
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SUMMARY

This document illustrates the generation/collection, archiving and processing strategies of HXC research data. According to the guidelines provided by the Horizon 2020, the project data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) as much as it is possible, except when there are substantial reasons to keep the data confidential.

This document describes the possible levels of data openness within the HealthXCross project, considering that the ethnographers have a duty to consider appropriate ways of making research materials publicly accessible when this will not violate ethical principles of ethnographic research. This will be possible with non-personal and non-processed data such as videos and pictures that do not harm people who can be identified (a release will be anyway needed), acquired dataset, bibliography. The personal non-processed data will NOT be freely available during the period of the project (unless otherwise stipulated with research participants) because this research is subject to GDPR privacy legislation.

Ethnographic data are part of a social context, therefore they are not easily reducible to a fixed and finished product. As such, it may not always be possible to make data interoperable. However, there is a number of data (e.g. archival research) that may be less sensitive and complex, thus in the middle of the HXC funding period the option to render specific data sets interoperable will be evaluated and, where deemed uncritical, it will be made.

For the same reasons, it may not always be possible to make data reusable. However, the question and the interest of re-use by third parties will be considered throughout the duration of the project and made a subject of reflection. In particular, collected and generated data could provide useful background information for similar projects.

The data of HXC project will have their origin from interviews (audio-recordings, transcripts, templates and notes of the researcher), fieldnotes, video, pictures, pseudonymised conversion files, informed consent files (templates and signed), acquired datasets (archival documents, statistics etc...), bibliography. The estimated data size is less than 100GB per case study, so the overall data size is expected to stay below 1 TB in total.

The following types/formats of data will be created, collected, stored and/or processed (here in alphabetical order):

- Acquired datasets (archival documents, statistics etc...) (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT, CSV, XLS);
- Bibliography (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT);
- Fieldnotes (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT);
- Informed consent (templates and signed) (DOC, PDF);

- Interviews (audio-recordings: MP3, WAV, AIFF, OGG, transcripts, templates and notes of the researcher: DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT);
- Pictures (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF);
- Pseudonymised conversion files (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT);
- Video (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4).

For the data archiving the G Drive storage and synchronization service developed by Google will be used. In G Drive space there is a 'HealthXCross' folder with many sub-folders. To archive research data, there is a folder named 'Research Data' and to store bibliography, a folder named 'Bibliography', with sub-folders corresponding to each researcher name. The structure of HXC research datasets will be organised following the data archiving strategy illustrated in the Section 2.5.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
G Drive	Google Drive
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HXC	HealthXCross
GA	Grant Agreement
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PI	Principal Investigator

Change Control

V	Date	Author	Description/Comments
1.0	15.11.2021	Roberta Raffaetà	First draft version
2.0			Input from Data Monitoring Board
2.1			Final version for submission
3.0			Review and corrections after 18 project months

The present document has been developed by taking as main reference four documents:

- 1) How to create your Data Management Plan for H2020 and HE. A practical guide (Ca' Foscari University of Venice) https://www.unive.it/pag/fileadmin/user_upload/ateneo/chi-siamo/organ-ateneo/data_monitoring_board/How_to_create_DMP_2-2021.pdf;
- 2) DMP guidelines provided by Leiden University CADS Institute <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/social-behavioural-sciences/cultural-anthropology-and-development-sociology/research/guidelines-protocols--policies#data-management-policy>;
- 4) EASA's Statement on Data Governance in Ethnographic Projects (European Association of Social Anthropologists) https://www.easaonline.org/downloads/support/EASASTatementon_data_governance.pdf.
- 3) A Data Governance Framework for Ethnography v. 1.0. (Alberto Corsín Jiménez, Spanish National Research Council) https://digital.csic.es/bitstream/10261/172227/3/data_governance_framework181115.pdf;

1. THE SPECIFICITIES OF HEALTHXCROSS PROJECT IN RELATION TO DATA

1.1 Description of the project

HealthXCross is a multi-sited ethnographic study that aspires to offer timely insights into the interplay between knowledge making and changing health practices in times of profound ecological, socio-technical and economic transition and to advance anthropological understandings of the contradictory but constitutive aspects of living together and being in relation.

HealthXCross will explore how microbiome research is reconfiguring concepts and practices of health, analysing how scientists innovate through open-data platforms. These platforms collect, compare and aggregate - through advanced AI technology - microbial data with other kinds of data (medical, environmental, social etc.) in the attempt of reconfiguring concepts and practices of health for intervening in both environmental and human health.

The project is committed to create symbiotic processes of research collaboration in the frame of open-data platforms with the scope to generate new knowledge in the experimental process across space, time, species and disciplines. By exploring how scientists advance science, it is possible to learn and foresee how society will change, and viceversa. In particular, the project will examine the following aspects of the research open data platforms:

- remake notions of biological diversity through technology by crossing conventional categorizations (space, time, species) and epistemic cultures;
- create and emerge from the diverse spacetimes of innovations across the global North and the global South;
- shape new trends in healthcare and health governance.

1.2 Anthropology and data management

Data management in the field of anthropological research is characterized by some specific aspects. First of all, ethnographic materials are coproduced by researchers and research participants and are embedded in particular social contexts: “Ethnographers recognise that social research is necessarily based in social relationships and therefore has to be built on a qualitative, intersubjective and value-laden foundation, usually based on mutual trust, so coproduced by researchers and researched. The co-production of data implies that data are rarely fully owned by either researcher or researched. The first duty of anthropologists and ethnographers towards science is therefore to recognise this joint production and joint ownership of data. All forms and norms of managing data depend on it.”¹. In the light of the collaborative nature of data the following commonly accepted anthropological procedures will be applied:

- the data gathered in an anthropological/ethnographic setting are held in the custody and possession by the researcher who protects the interests of people studied or be returned to them (if possible), unless otherwise stipulated. When research is being done among multiple parties in conflict with each other (or where it would violate individual's privacy to return data to a collective/group), the data will be held in trust by the researcher;

¹ Pels, P., & al., e. (2018). Data management in anthropology: the next phase in ethics governance? *Social Anthropology*, 26(3), 391–413.

- the data will be safely stored and preserved by individual researchers until their retirement from actual research reporting, when they will be returned to research participants, destroyed or placed in an appropriate archive (see below), unless otherwise stipulated;
- the data can only be shared with third parties after they have been processed to safeguard the privacy and intellectual/cultural property of research participants, depending on the ethical judgement of the researcher, unless otherwise stipulated.

As stated in the DMP guidelines provided by Leiden University CADS Institute², in the process of anthropological/ethnographic research, social relationships with research participants are usually dynamic, qualitative and personal and require constant revision of the standards of research participants' privacy and cultural property. Researchers are responsible for protecting the research participants' interests, by keeping the data in a well-documented secluded setting unless they have been processed for third party consumption. Anthropological data are not stored in excel sheets or databases, but in the form of lengthy written texts that span multiple hand-written notebooks and/or digital files (e.g. word docs, photos, film, audio-recordings). These data require contextualization to be intelligible to other researchers because:

- they reflect a human relationship between researcher and research participants that shapes the context in which the data was gathered;
- each notebook, or text, cannot be easily understood without triangulation across multiple notebooks/devices/personal archives, which cannot all be made available due to the risk of breach of privacy (lack of anonymity);
- without deep knowledge of the research context, of the broader social situation/conversation/physical location in which the notes were gathered, and of the specific research participants' privacy and data protection the data cannot be accurately interpreted.

These principles translate into various elements for a data management policy that include open access publishing where possible, confidentiality and safety for research participants, and transparency about use and storage of data. What above has some direct consequences on data collection and processing:

- the recording of anthropological/ethnographic data, whether in written, oral or visual form, is a dynamic process of collaboration to which research participants have given and continue to give their consent during fieldwork (this does not imply their agreement with findings), including conditions pertaining to analysis and publication.
- the changing relationships of confidentiality and mutual trust established during this research process are of utmost importance in providing, collecting and processing research data.
- researchers should continue to treat data as collaborative for as long as they work with this material, acknowledging that these data – in variable gradations – may be co-owned by researchers and the researched.
- individual researchers have the duty to subordinate the sharing of data with third parties (including other scientists, also in cases of investigating fraud) to the recognition of the collaborative nature of data.

² <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/social-behavioural-sciences/cultural-anthropology-and-development-sociology/research/guidelines-protocols--policies#data-management-policy>

2. MAKING DATA FINDABLE

2.1 Definition of data

Non-processed and processed data

The nature of ethnographic research makes it difficult to distinguish between raw and processed data because data gathered in an anthropological/ethnographic setting are always the outcome of the co-production of a researcher with research participants. This has two main implications: 1) the term ‘non-processed data’ is to prefer to ‘raw data’; 2) the distinction between non-processed and processed data differs, depending on whether the audience in question is interested in mere verification, publication or reuse. The making of that distinction, and therefore the providing access to the data concerned, is the ethical responsibility of the researcher. For the purpose of data fairification, however, a distinction between non-processed data and data processed for audience consumption can be made.

Non-processed data

Within this category a distinction should be made between personal and non-personal data:

- Personal non-processed data: in the context of HXC these are fieldnotes, audio of interviews, conversion files, approved informed consent and - when including people who can be identified - videos and pictures. These requires the greatest care in handling (highlighted in red in the Fig. 1 below) because contain information that may lead to the identification of an individual, personalized data and cultural properties that are never anonymised and can therefore not be openly accessed. Providing access to personalized, and possibly sensitive, non-processed data could harm the people studied (see American Anthropological Association Code of Ethics <http://www.aaanet.org/profdev/ethics>). For the duration of project only the researcher (or research team) will have direct access to personal, non-processed data. If the research team plans to share those types of data, this should be clearly communicated to the research participants. Anyone outside of the research team (including assistants) who is granted access to the raw data will be asked to sign a non-disclosure agreement. Only the researcher who gathered the data will be empowered to decide who can be granted access to which research materials, and in which formats, and will do so in accordance with the current legislation valid at the time of the research and/or research reporting.
- Non-personal and non-processed data: in HXC these are acquired datasets, bibliography, videos and pictures in which people cannot be identified.

Processed data

Within the HXC project, processed data are informed consent templates, pseudonymised interview transcripts, templates and notes. In their autonomy – without being associated to the pseudonyms conversion files - they still are non-personal data.

	Personal	Non-personal	Processed	Non-processed
Interview audio	X			X
Interview notes		X	X	
Interview transcripts		X	X	
Interview templates		X	X	
Fieldnotes	X			X
Video/pictures (with personal identification)	X			X
Video/pictures (without personal identification)		X		X
Pseudo/real names conversion files	X			X
Informed consent templates		X	X	
Informed consent signed	X			X
Acquired datasets		X		X
Bibliography		X		X

Fig. 1. Summary of research data types according to the 'personal/non-personal' e 'processed/non-processed' categories.

2.2 HXC types of data

The following types of data will be created, collected, stored and/or processed (here in alphabetical order):

- Acquired datasets (archival documents, statistics etc...);
- Bibliography;
- Fieldnotes;
- Informed consent (templates and signed);
- Interviews (audio-recordings, transcripts, templates and notes of the researcher);
- Pictures;
- Pseudonymised conversion files;
- Video.

Acquired datasets

This category encompasses a broad and heterogeneous material, acquired from digital and non-digital sources such as public archives, newspapers, websites. Examples of these data: archival documents, statistics, maps, pictures, videos, etc...

Bibliography

Bibliography is intended as a list of all of the sources used in the HXC process of researching and it comprises books, research articles, reports, online presentation, etc.

Fieldnotes

Participant observation is the main ethnographic method. The participation in the social situation studies combined with its observation allow for the generation of insights that would not be possible with other methods. In participant observation, the researcher is both an insider (participation) and outsider (observation) and the tension between these two apparently contradictory stances is what give value to this methodology. But it is also a complex approach, therefore it is important to keep track of both what happens in the situation observed and of the subjective feelings and ideas of the researcher. Fieldnotes are written observations recorded during or immediately following participant observations in the field and are considered critical to understanding phenomena encountered in the field. Therefore, they usually (especially in the first stages of the fieldwork) display research participants' real names. Fieldnotes will be combined with interviews and other research material.

Informed consent

Informed consent is one of the central components of the ethical conduct of research with human subjects. The intent of informed consent is to provide to the research participants full information about what it means for them to take part, and that they give consent before they enter the research process. This category contains templates (no personal data) and signed documents with personal data filled in by research participant.

Interviews

Participant observation is often combined with in-depth interviews. These are semi-structured interviews that follow an open and flexible template that help the researcher to have clear in mind the main topic that should be addressed. During the interview, however, the researcher should be open and ready to allow deviation from the planned template, to follow the interviewee's line of reasoning (what she/he deem important, how these aspects are presented and prioritized etc...) The interviewees considered in the HXC ethnographic studies will mostly be scientists working in laboratories in microbiology/computational and/or biology/genetics/veterinary/medicine fields of expertise. Information collected essentially covers scientists' knowledge and practices related to microbiome science/planetary health. Interviews, as data, consist of the interview template, researcher's notes taken during the interview, the interview's audio-recording (if agreed) and the interview's transcript. Audio are considered personal data, while notes and transcripts can be pseudonymised and the interviewee's contact details (e.g. name, surname, email address) won't be recorded in the interview transcript/note and kept separate from it.

Pictures and Videos

Pictures and video are intended as a digital tool that supports the observation method. They will be useful to triangulate observations tracked with other methods, strengthening the robustness of the overall analysis. This allows observers to be guided in taking notes on central phenomena and allowing them to add notes on other phenomena. Pictures and videos can or cannot contain personal data. These visual data may be also used as a form of restitution to research participants because its visual nature may trigger interesting discussions. Pictures and videos are also a powerful and useful way to disseminate knowledge to a broader public. Audio-video recordings collected during research activities will be immediately archived in the PI and team members' computers (and deleted from the camera). The file will be encrypted and protected by password, then transferred to the Host Institution Google Drive web service.

Conversion files (real names vs pseudo)

The real interviewees' names collected during the research activities will be converted in the pseudonymised ones. This conversion process will be tracked using the conversion files. In this way the personal data will be kept separate from the real names. The interviewees, therefore, cannot be identified from the pseudonymised name (unless otherwise agreed).

2.3 Data origin and life flow

Acquired datasets

These data will be acquired from digital and non-digital sources such as public archives, newspapers, websites and will be likely open access and public. If not, HXC team will adhere to the privacy and security measures requested from the data provider. Acquired datasets will be stored in a digital device (laptop, PC) and in G Drive.

Bibliography

The data belonging to this category will be downloaded from bibliographic platforms and stored in a digital device (laptop, PC) and in G Drive.

Conversion files

These files will be created in Word format (or equivalent) in a digital device with encryption and password-protected. The conversion files will be temporarily stored in a laptop, and then transferred as soon as possible in G Drive, possible with a closed access, and deleted from original sources. No one but the researcher who has created this file will be able to access it.

Fieldnotes

These will be taken on paper and/or a through a digital device (smartphone, laptop or PC) protected by password and with file encryption. In case of digital devices, files used will be Word (or equivalent).

If in paper, sheets will be stored in a secure and locked place.

If digital files, these will be stored as soon as possible in G Drive and deleted from original sources.

Informed consent

This category contains templates (no personal data) and signed documents with personal data, created in Word (or equivalent). The templates will be stored in a digital device (laptop, PC password-protected and encrypted) and in G Drive. The signed informed consent with personal data will be temporarily stored in a laptop, and then transferred as soon as possible in G Drive and deleted from original sources.

Interviews

Templates: created in Word (or equivalent) to guide the interview.

Notes: taken on a paper diary and/or a through a digital device (smartphone, laptop or PC) protected by password through a common format file such as Word (or similar). If in paper, sheets will be stored in a secure and locked place. If digital files, these will be stored as soon as possible in G Drive and deleted from original sources.

Audio: taken through a recorder (dedicated device, smartphone or PC/laptop recorder with password and encryption), stored as soon as possible in G Drive and deleted from the original sources. Alternatively, recordings may be taken via online transcription services apps such as Otter.ai (English only), Word Transcribe (English only), Sonix (more languages). These apps all state to comply with GDPR regulation. Anyway, to enhance security, files will be exported as soon as possible to G Drive and deleted from the app.

Transcript: Ethnography includes a high number of interviews, therefore these online transcription services are very useful in saving time and energy, making the flow of the research much more efficient. If working with highly vulnerable groups, these services should be avoided. In the case of HXC, however, this procedure is feasible since the likelihood of data leakage and associated risks are minimal. Only in case interviews will be planned (or will develop) to contain highly confidential data, e.g. akin to industrial intelligence or special categories of data, the researcher will not use online transcription services and we will proceed to traditional recording techniques and

manual transcription. Transcription files using pseudonyms will be stored as soon as possible in G Drive and, after checking the appropriateness of the transcription (especially in case of online, automated transcription services), deleted from original sources.

Pictures and Videos

Pictures and videos will be taken with dedicated (video)camera or smartphones (video)camera with file encryption and password. These files will be stored as soon as possible in G Drive and deleted from original sources.

2.4 Overall data size

The estimated data size is less than 100GB per case study, so the overall data size is expected to stay below 1 TB in total.

2.5 Archiving structure and naming conventions

In this section the archiving and naming conventions within G Drive are illustrated. This should be taken as a provisional design, to be adapted to the real needs and features of the fieldwork and to the specificities of each case study. Possible amendment will be reported in following versions of this document.

In G Drive there is a 'HXC_Research' folder with sub-folders. To archive research data, there is a folder named 'Research Data'. To store bibliography, a folder named 'Bibliography'.

Research Data

In the 'Research Data' folder, the categorization logic that structures HXC data archiving strategy is primarily 'by subject', and this corresponds to HXC case studies. In the 'Research Data' folder, sub-folders will be so organized:

Level 1: HXC case studies. Folders corresponding to the name of the researcher dedicated to that specific case study

Level 2: Each case study will have sub-folders corresponding to specific fields locations

Level 3: Within specific locations, there will be four sub-folders: 'Interviews', 'Field' and 'Ethics'

Level 4a: Within the 'Interviews' folder, there will be four sub-folders, corresponding to four types of data:

1) Templates

In this folder, files will be so named:

Research participant name_Date_Location_Researcher name (initials)_Template_Interview

Ex: Maria_220921_UCSD_RR_Template_Interview

2) 'Notes': Researchers notes during interview

In this folder, files will be so named:

Research participant name_Date_Location_Researcher name (initials)_Notes_Interview

Ex: Maria_220921_UCSD_RR_Notes_Interview

3) 'Rec': Audiorecording (if agreed)

In this folder, files will be so named:

Research participant name_Date_Location_Researcher name (initials)_Rec_Interview

Ex: Maria_220921_UCSD_RR_Rec_Interview

4) 'Transcripts': transcription of audiorecordings

In this folder, files will be so named:

Research participant name_Date_Location_Researcher name (initials)_Transcript_Interview

Ex: Maria_220921_UCSD_RR_Transcript_Interview

Level 4b: Within the 'Field' folder, there will be four sub-folders, corresponding to four types of data:

1) 'Fieldnotes'

In this folder, files will be so named:

Date_Location_Researchername(initials)_Field_Fieldnotes

Ex: 220921_UCSD_RR_Field_Fieldnotes

To facilitate analysis, it would be better that this file is a single one, updated with new data (each section has a data)

2) 'Pics'

This folder will be freely organized by the researcher

3) 'Video'

This folder will be freely organized by the researcher

4) 'Acquired dataset'

It will contain heterogeneous material, organized according to its content (e.g. archival data, statistics, newspaper articles, images, etc...) in ways specific to each case study.

Level 4c: Within the 'Ethics' folder, there will be two sub-folders, corresponding to two types of data:

1) 'Informed consent'

In this folder, files will be so named:

Research participant name_Informedconsent_Annex1/2/3_Location_Researchername(initials)_Date

Ex: Maria_Informedconsent_Annex1_UCSD_RR_220921

2) 'Conversion files' (real names vs pseudo)

In this folder, files will be so named:

Location_Date_Researchername(initials)_Conversion

Ex1: UCSD_220921_RR_Conversion

RESEARCH DATA

Fig. 2. Research data archiving structure.

Bibliography

In the ‘Bibliography’ folder, sub-folders will be organized with sub-folders corresponding to each researcher name and each researcher will organize bibliography creating thematic sub-folders (e.g. One Health, Microbiome, Africa, Asia, etc....). In these folders, there will be scientific publications files (external) and they will be named making reference to the author, title and date of publication:

Ex1: Helmreich_Alienoccean_2016

These PDF will be synced with the Zotero platform for bibliographic archiving.

2.6 Metadata

The metadata populating G Drive are:

- Bibliography
- Conversion
- Date
- Field
- Fieldnotes
- Interviews
- Location
- Notes
- Pic
- Pseudo
- Rec
- Researcher name
- Research participant name
- Signed
- Templates
- Transcript
- Video

These make data findable and are first of all for use internal to the HXC team. For metadata open to others, see Section 4.

3. MAKING DATA OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.1 Accessibility

Non-processed data

Personal non-processed data will NOT be freely available during the period of the project (unless otherwise stipulated with research participants, see next section) because this research is subject to GDPR legal framework, in particular in reference to the protection of personal data. This choice also adheres to current anthropological codes of ethics (AAA and EASA). Ethnographic data require a dialogue between the research who collected them and who want to see/reuse them because they are scarcely understandable out of their context of collection.

As illustrated in the DMP guidelines provided by Leiden University CADS Institute³, ethnographic data is usually gathered in note form based on a close and personal interaction between researcher and research participant. The data is not stored in the form of words or numbers in a database. Ethnographic notes are stored in hand-written notebooks and/or digital text files. Because ethnographic data contains a great deal of information about people's lives, even if the notes are technically anonymised, anonymity could potentially be breached if whole sets of notes were viewed together and triangulated with each other. The researcher therefore must carefully select which data can be made public. The impossibility of making all the data available, means that the available data might not be transferable or useful/decipherable to other researchers except through direct conversation with the researcher who can give more ethnographic details, without sharing any personal information which may lead to the identification of individuals.

In anthropological research, the thought process and position of the researcher (fieldnotes) is considered relevant information for the accurate contextualization and interpretation of research materials, and as such, this information is often written down and only some of this highly private information is acceptable for public circulation. The inextricability of anthropological field notes in which all of the conversations (private and public) as well as the reflexive analytical thoughts of the researcher and research participants are maintained in one set of notebooks or files, means that one of the most important data management tasks is determining which data can be publicly shared (=made into processed data for dissemination) and which cannot. The process of choosing what data can be shared and what cannot be, requires knowledge of the field, of the research participants, and of the specific moment, context and human relationship between researcher and research participant that brought the data into being. Only the researcher has this knowledge.

³ <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/social-behavioural-sciences/cultural-anthropology-and-development-sociology/research/guidelines-protocols--policies#data-management-policy>

As addressed in the EASA's Statement on Data Governance in Ethnographic Projects⁴, in ethnographic research "data" are always part of a social relationship. The collaborative but also sensitive nature of ethnographic research implies that ethnographers have a special duty to consider requests by research participants (or their descendants) to share materials, unless this actively and unnecessarily harms (some of) them. Ethnographers also have a duty to consider appropriate ways of making research materials publicly accessible when this will not violate ethical principles of ethnographic research, data protection and IP law. This will be possible with non-personal and non-processed data such as videos and pictures that do not harm people who can be identified (a prior authorization will be anyway needed), acquired dataset, bibliography.

Processed data

Some data are non-personal and processed from the start (such as templates) and they can be shared. With the aim to try to increase data accessibility and re-use, personal data will be processed to make them pseudonymized. In particular, in case of interviews, recordings will be transcribed and pseudonyms will be used. Pseudonymized interviews, without the possibility to triangulate it with other personalised data (e.g. fieldnotes and pseudonymous conversion file) can be considered by itself really close to the concept of anonymized data. Therefore, most of the case extracts from the interview will be used in publications.

However, this kind of data - triangulated with other data in a publication or presentation – still may lead to indirect identification. Therefore, before sending manuscripts to journals/editors/colleagues or cite quotes at public events (such as conferences), the research participants involved will be given opportunity to read the draft.

At this stage, sometimes research participants request their real names to be disclosed considering the collaborative nature of ethnography. Especially in the case of scientists, these research participants prefer greater, rather than less, sharing of the data they contributed to science. In case of making openly accessible their real names, a further informed consent will be granted by the participant.

In case of videos and pictures in which would be possible to identify persons, if any data will be selected to disseminate research insights, research participants will be given the opportunity to visualize the data that portray them and to consent/authorisation to their dissemination or not.

Tiered consent options

In sum, HealthXCross has tiered consent options. The process of consent includes these main steps, their number depending from the specific situation, as described below and represented in Fig.3:

Step 1 - Provide information about the project (via voice and Annex1: Informed_consent)

Step 2 - To those interested in participating in the project, request signature of the Informed consent, including the collection and processing of special categories of data (Annex 1: Informed_consent)

Step 3 - In case of collection of audio-visual data connected to personal data, request signature of the Release form of audio-visuals (Annex 2: Release_audiovisuals).

Step 4 - In case some of the data gathered will be considered by research participants as exceptionally sensitive, and akin to industrial intelligence, non-disclosure agreement will be negotiated and signed by both parties (the researcher and the head of the lab).

Step 5 - In case research participants request direct identification after the viewing of the finished product (publication or else), request the relevant option' signature of the informed consent (Annex 3: Realnames)

⁴ <https://www.easaonline.org/downloads/support/EASASTatementonDataGovernance.pdf>

Fig. 3. Consent options stages.

Consent in anthropological research

Even if preference will be given to signed informed consent, in ethnographic research informal and even verbal consent is customary under certain conditions. In the process of anthropological/ethnographic research specifically, social relationships with research participants are usually dynamic, qualitative and personal and require constant revision of the standards of research participants' privacy and cultural property. Verbal consent, if obtained in specific situations, is in line with GDPR requirements too, if is preceded by giving to participants an information sheet with all information about data processing. In case verbal consent will be secured, this will be audio-video recorded as evidence.

Definition of 'research participant' in the context of HXC

To contextualize what above, it is important to give a precise definition of 'research participants' in HXC. A research participant is someone who is personally involved in the project (via direct observation of her/his behaviours, collection of casual sentences, picture, audio-visuals and/or interview) and gives consent to it. For example, labs or project consortiums include a number of people who will not be directly involved in the study. They will be

considered as third parties and informed consent will not be asked to them. This also safeguards the scientific aspects of ethnography, which is sometimes irreducible to consent. Ethnographic participation in a social milieu lends itself to dynamics that are hardly controllable by the researcher and for which it is not always possible to obtain consent. Yet, these conditions – as stated in the section above - comply with GDPR. Finally, it should be considered that scientists are particular a category: they cannot be considered a vulnerable group because they have a high educational level that permits them to understand the implications of research.

3.2 Who will access data and level of accessibility

HXC research group will use processed and non-processed data for internal meetings and processed data to write reports, academic journal articles, books and book chapters. HXC team will also present the results of the project at seminars, workshop and conferences and will display some selected and processed data on the website and social media. Of those activities participants will be informed adequately and consent will be asked for further dissemination of research result when dealing with personal data.

3.2.1 Internal use

Data stored in GDrive: these data will be for internal use (shared only between HXC project researchers from Ca' Foscari university). Fieldnotes, audio and notes of interviews, consent forms and pseudo conversion will be confidential, that is data only accessible by the researcher who has collected them. Video and pictures which contain personal data will be retained by the single researcher who has collected them too. Other kinds of video/pictures, templates, bibliography files and files (if not bind to confidentiality) can be accessible by the team members.

Confidential:

Interview audio
Interview notes
Fieldnotes
Video/pictures
Signed informed consent
Conversion file

Team:

Informed consent templates
Bibliography
Interview transcripts and templates
Video/pictures

3.2.2 OA publications

Data that appear in OA publications and at public presentations/media are considered public: they can be made public at any time during or after the project. HXC team members will give preference to publishing in journals that allow diamond open access. In alternative, green open access and, as last option, gold open access.

3.2.3 Repositories

This is not an option at the initial stage of the project. In the case that, during the project, the PI will decide to store some data in repositories (e.g. Zenodo/Dataverse), it can be envisaged that most of these will be stored with restricted access: access is restricted due to a period of embargo or if only certain people can access it after having contacted the researcher.

3.3 Software

The following types and formats of documents will be used:

- Text documents (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT);
- Images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF);
- Video/film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4);
- Audio (MP3, WAV, AIFF, OGG);
- Table (CSV, XLS).

4. MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Ethnographic data are part of a social context, therefore they are not easily reducible to a fixed and finished product. As such, it may not always be possible to make data interoperable. However, there is a number of data (e.g. archival research) that may be less sensitive and complex, thus in the middle of the HXC funding period the option to render specific data sets interoperable will be evaluated and, where deemed uncritical, it will be made.

In case data will be stored in repositories (e.g. Zenodo), metadata will be created according to the Dublin Core standard, see <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>. According to this standard, terms used are:

- | | | |
|---------------|---------------|---------------------|
| • Title | • Contributor | • Language |
| • Creator | • Date | • Identifier |
| • Subject | • Type | • Rights management |
| • Description | • Format | |

5. INCREASE DATA RE-USE

At the start of the HXC project, the re-use of data by third parties cannot be pre-defined before each case study is well-advanced given the sensitivity of ethnographic data and their necessary embeddedness in specific social contexts. Ethnographic data deprived of contextual data would be scientifically meaningless. Ethnographic data are not easily reducible to a fixed and finished product. As such, it may not always be possible to make data reusable. However, the question and the interest of re-use by third parties will be considered throughout the duration of the project and made a subject of reflection. In particular, collected and generated data could provide useful background information for similar projects.

The specification of data reuse will be an issue for the mid-term report (month 30) and will be finally decided upon at the end of the HXC funding-period. In that occasion, if appropriate, the PI will identify the appropriate usage license for each kind of dataset.

6. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES and DATA SECURITY

6.1. Costs

No costs related to technical equipment and infrastructure will be incurred for making the collected data FAIR (as meant in this document), as the tools used are already at the project disposal (Microsoft Office and Adobe Acrobat) or have been put at its disposal free of charge (the *Resource Space* made available by Ca' Foscari University). The cost in term of time will impact on the time that researchers can allocate to other aspects of their research.

In the case that, in the middle or end of the project, it will be decided to archive some data/metadata on platforms such as Zenodo/Dataverse for reuse, the project manager of HXC will support in this. If, after the end of the project, necessary resources will have to be found.

6.2 Responsibilities

Responsible for data management are the data sets creators (the researchers responsible for each case study) who are directly involved in research data organisation and collection. Data quality will be assured through a close supervision of each case study by the PI. The PI maintains access to the data to prove the scientific integrity of the project, for backups and replications, and for future research developments. Moreover, schemes for the documentation of all HXC research data and their relevance in the research process will provide a framework for structured and reflected work across sub-projects. As for data protection, the data controller is Ca' Foscari University.

The single researcher who acts for the University is the person appointed to personal data processing; notwithstanding this, he/she has to take any action on behalf of the University for respecting the obligations set out by the data protection law. If there are substantial suspicions of academic fraud or other breaches of academic integrity by members of the research team, an official investigation committee can, under strict conditions, be given access to the data stored in G Drive. HXC researchers will employ informatic tools such as G Drive and Zoom, which have been already appointed as data processors by the data controller

6.3 Data storage and backup

Custodianship is an important aspect of ethnographic research. Researchers have a scientific and ethical responsibility to preserve and protect the integrity of ethnographic materials. This is a responsibility that is usually negotiated with research participants because forms of custodianship, caretaking or archiving cannot always be anticipated or pre-formatted. As a rule, in HXC, non-processed personal research data are stored and preserved by the PI and her team up to a max of 5 years after the end of the project (in the specific ways detailed in Section 2.3 of this document), when they will be destroyed or returned to (heir of) the research participants, unless otherwise stipulated.

In this time length, data is held under the university host institution without public disclosure. G Drive is a secured online service certified by Ca' Foscari University of Venice that is being used extensively for data management and protection. A folder dedicated to HXC research data will only be accessible to the researchers in this project. It will be also accessible during fieldwork so data can be stored immediately. G Drive is currently being used for data retention for a wide range of projects, including those funded by the ERC.

Data types	Where and for how long to store
Fieldnotes (personal, non-processed)	-pass-protected and encrypted PC/laptop (temporarily) -G Drive (up to 5 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: only if anonymised
Interviews – audio (personal, non-processed)	-pass-protected and encrypted PC/laptop (temporarily) -G Drive (up to 5 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: NA
Interviews – transcripts (non-personal, processed)	-PC/laptop and back-up in personal hard-disk (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -G Drive (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: OK
Interviews – notes (non-personal, processed)	-PC/laptop and back-up in personal hard-disk (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -G Drive (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: OK
Video/pictures with personal identification (personal, non-processed)	-pass-protected and encrypted PC/laptop (temporarily) -G Drive (up to 5 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: NA
Video/pictures without personal identification (non-personal, non-processed)	-PC/laptop and back-up in personal hard-disk (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -G Drive (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: OK
Pseudo/real names conversion files (personal, non-processed)	-pass-protected and encrypted PC/laptop (temporarily) -G Drive (up to 5 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: NA
Informed consent templates (non-personal, processed)	-PC/laptop and back-up in personal hard-disk (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -G Drive (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: OK
Signed informed consent (personal, non-processed)	-pass-protected and encrypted PC/laptop (temporarily) -G Drive (up to 5 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: NA
Acquired datasets (non-personal, non-processed)	-PC/laptop and back-up in personal hard-disk (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -G Drive (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: OK
Bibliography (non-personal, non-processed)	-PC/laptop and back-up in personal hard-disk (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -G Drive (up to 20 yrs by the end of the project) -Repositories: OK

Fig. 4. Data storage location and duration per data type.

6.4 Value of long-term data preservation

Anthropological research is often hard to divide into clearly delineated projects with a start date and an end date. Instead, anthropologists tend to build their knowledge of a subject or a group of people continuously over decades or over a whole career. As such, data are usually stored and maintained long-term. Both the storage and the sharing of data comply with the GDPR regulations (= no sharing of personal information without consent, the researcher has weighed the relative right to privacy of the research participants carefully against the public interest served by the research and has ensured that raw and processed data are stored in safe, or the safest possible, locations).

Anthropological research is often of great archival value and researchers should consider whether their data can be safely archived long-term after the end of a research project. Not all data will be safe for public archiving, but the public interest potentially served by making ethnographic archives (partially) available at the end of a research project or researcher's career should be considered prior to the destruction of research data.

In the context of HXC project, research data will be archived up to 5 yrs by the end of the project if there are personal data (except otherwise stipulated with the research participants themselves) and for non-personal data up to 20 years after the end of the project. Where such archival plans differ from those originally included in this DMP, an amended DMP will be submitted.

Annexes for ERC project 949742 - HealthXCross

Addendum	Document title/file name/description	Applicable to entire project/ project part (please specify)	Issued by
Annex 1	Information Sheet with informed consent	Entire project	PI-Host Institution (approved)
Annex 2	Release for images, video and audio recordings.	Entire project	PI-Host Institution (approved)
Annex 3	Informed consent for de-anonymisation	Entire project	PI-Host Institution (approved)

INFORMATION SHEET

Title of the Project: 949742 – HealthXCross – ERC Starting Grant (2021-2026)

What is the project about? Theme and expected impact of the project

My name is Roberta Raffaetà, and I am Associate Professor at Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Dept. of Philosophy and Cultural Heritage. I have received funding from the European Research Council (2021-2026) to analyse, with the help of other researchers part of my team, how scientists produce and coordinate knowledge within interdisciplinary platforms that compare and integrate data across time, space and species, and what are the impact of this research in terms of health concepts and practices. The project is for my own independent research and is not connected to any industry. By exploring how scientists advance science, it is possible to learn and foresee how society will change, and viceversa. The project, therefore, has the overall aim to strengthen the interaction between science and society through evaluation and communication. Your participation will also help to improve interdisciplinary research, education programs and policies.

What is involved with being a participant in the project? Methods of the project

Two main methods will involve research participants: 1) participant observation, 2) semi-structured interviews. Participant observation: a researcher will join a social situation (a meeting, lab work, etc...) observing it. During participant observation, the researcher may also make some video and take pictures. Semi-structured interviews: willing persons will be interviewed by the project's researcher. The researcher will propose a main theme (2-3 main questions) to be developed by the interviewee. The interview may last few minutes to hours, depending on the interviewee's willingness to elaborate and interact. Participation in interviews is entirely voluntary and arranged at a time and a place that suits the interviewee. The interviewee can skip questions who doesn't want to answer or can choose not to finish any part of the interview. In the context of this project, a research participant is defined as someone of whom we will collect personal data (ideas, pictures, audio-visuals) and gives consent to it. For example, labs or project consortiums include a number of people who will not be directly involved in the study and of whom we will not collect personal data. These will be considered 'third parties'.

Privacy and pseudonymization

Interviews: upon agreement, the interview will be taped to make sure that the researcher will not miss anything, but the interviewee's name won't be recorded in the interview transcript and kept separate from it, as indicated by art. 4(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679-General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The interviewees, therefore, cannot be identified from the name (unless otherwise agreed). Ethnographic interviews, however, are often saturated by personal information because they consist of those kinds of knowledge that determine social life. The processing of personal data may reveal ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health and data concerning a sex life or sexual orientation and therefore they may lead to indirect identification. For this reason, before to publish any paper/book that relates directly to some to research participant, we will share the manuscripts with her/him (if participants give the consent to it). They can withdraw consent for its use if feeling that anything that is written is causing discomfort or any potential threat.

Audio-visual data: due to the fact that these involve a higher probability that participants may be identified, we will follow up initial consent given by research participants with a reaffirmation of the consent for further disseminate it, and by negotiations about ownership of and access to the recordings and conditions of publication.

Participants can withdraw from participation in the project or parts of it if they change their mind later. This can be done by telephoning me or one of the research team members or putting this request in writing, for example in an email, without the need to give any reason. There are no consequences for withdrawing at any time, with effect from the day of its request and it is *ex nunc*, not affecting the research products already published/presented.

Data access and archiving

No one but the researchers will have access to personal data such as interview recordings, fieldnotes, video, pictures, signed informed consent and pseudonyms conversion file. These will be stored in research team's computers, encrypted and protected by password, along with other IT measures to enhance data protection. The documents related to the research project (which may include your personal data) may be accessed by national and international bodies, by Italian and international journals committees in order to evaluate the lawfulness and fairness of the research conducted. Personal data may also be accessed by auditors. Research data will be archived up to 5 yrs by the end of the project if there are

personal data (except otherwise stipulated with the research participants themselves) and for non-personal data up to 20 years after the end of the project.

Third party policy

It is possible that the ethnography will include some non-working time and activities during which participants interact with third parties, but the focus will be on research participants and their relation to that third party – not the third party itself. I'll take all the precaution possible in any given situation to exclude third parties – especially children or others unable to consent - from the research interaction. No focused systematized data such as interviews or other will be collected about third parties.

Unexpected findings policy

Every ethnographic relationship resulting in reliable knowledge is built on mutual trust. However, in presence of unexpected findings such as illegal activities or findings of a sensitive nature with the potential to harm humanity, this trust can be overruled by values of a higher order.

Non-disclosure agreement

There is the possibility that some of the data gathered may be exceptionally sensitive, and akin to industrial intelligence. In relation to these kind of data, project's researchers will sign a non-disclosure agreement with the respective laboratories, to be negotiated before starting fieldwork. It will provide a clear definition of boundaries to preserve intellectual property and a basis for mutual trust and productive collaboration. For the data covered by the non-disclosure agreement, research participants will be enabled to claim their intellectual property at any time during data gathering and processing.

Data processing and sharing

Personal data such as interview recordings, fieldnotes, video, pictures, signed informed consent and pseudonyms conversion files will be accessible only by the University of Venice researcher who collected them within the HealthXCross project. Selected processed data may be used to write reports, academic journal articles, books and book chapters. The team will also present the results of the project at seminars, workshop and conferences and will display some selected and processed data on the website and associated social media.

Who can I contact for more information?

Please feel free to contact me at any time for more information. I would welcome any queries at any time. My contact details are below.

Thank you,

Roberta Raffaetà

P: 0039 3382846103

roberta.raffaeta@unive.it

PRIVACY NOTICE FOR RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS PROJECT ERC 'HealthXCross' (GA 949742)

in accordance with art. 13 of EU Regulation 2016/679 ("Regulation")

In this privacy notice, Ca' Foscari University of Venice ('University') will provide you with information on the collection of your personal data from the ERC HealthXCross (GA 949742) research project. For further information about the research project, see the Information Sheet above. If you have any question, please do not hesitate to contact the Principal Investigator by writing to the email address: roberta.raffaeta@unive.it

The research project has been developed in accordance with the sector's research standards and policies and it is stored at the Department of Philosophy and Cultural Heritage of Ca' Foscari University of Venice where it will be retained for 5 years after the conclusion of the research.

1. DATA CONTROLLER

The data controller is Ca' Foscari University of Venice, with headquarters in Dorsoduro n. 3246, 30123 Venice (VE), legally represented by the Rector.

2. DATA PROTECTION OFFICER

The University has appointed a "Data Protection Officer" ('DPO'), who can be contacted by writing to the email address: dpo@unive.it or to the following address: Ca' Foscari University, Venice, Data Protection Officer, Dorsoduro n. 3246, 30123 Venice (VE).

3. PERSONAL DATA CATEGORIES, PURPOSES AND LEGAL BASIS OF DATA PROCESSING

We will collect a range of personal data in order to carry out the research project activities. This may include personal data such as the participants' name, surname, contact details, experiences, emails, recorded interviews, pictures and videos. We may also collect, in certain situations, special categories of personal data, notably data related to racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health, data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation or data relating to criminal convictions and offences. We will collect this information in a variety of ways, such as through fieldnotes, audio and/or video recordings, interviews.

The processing of personal data will be carried out with the use of computerised procedures, adopting appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect it from unauthorised or illegal access, destruction, loss of integrity and confidentiality, even if accidental in nature.

In order to protect the confidentiality of the participants, the information collected will be de-identified, which means that all direct identifiers (such as name, surname, etc.) will be removed and replaced by a pseudonym instead. Therefore, the participants will no longer be directly identifiable from the data. The key for re-identification will be archived up to 5 yrs by the end of the project, then it will be irreversibly deleted.

The research activities are conducted by the University in the public interest as part of its official functions, therefore the legal basis for the processing of personal data is represented by art. 6.1.e) of the Regulation ("performance of a task carried out in the public interest").

With regards to the processing of special categories of personal data, the legal basis is represented by art. 9.2.a) of the Regulation ("explicit consent of the data subject") in connexion with art. 7.2 of "Regole deontologiche", Allegato A5 to D.Lgs. n. 196/2003. Therefore, at the end of this document, in case these data will be collected, we will ask for your consent to collect and process this type of personal data. You can withdraw your consent at any time without prejudice, writing to me or to the DPO at the contact details mentioned below. We will stop the processing of your personal data unless there are compelling legitimate grounds to carry on with the processing.

With regards to the usage of your email or your address and your name and surname in order to being recontacted before the publication/presentation of research products, the legal basis is represented by art. 6.1.a) of the GDPR ('consent'). You can withdraw your consent at any time without prejudice, writing to me or to the DPO at the above mentioned contact details.

With regards to the – eventually agreed - usage of your name and surname for the publications and other research products related to the research activities, such as interviews which have been conducted, the legal basis is represented by art. 6.1.a) of the GDPR ('consent'). You can withdraw your consent at any time without prejudice, writing to me or to the DPO at the above mentioned contact details. The withdrawal of the consent has effect from the day of its request and it is *ex nunc*, not affecting the research products already published/presented.

4. DATA RETENTION

Research data will be archived up to 5 yrs by the end of the project if there are personal data (except otherwise stipulated with the research participants themselves) and for non-personal data up to 20 years after the end of the project.

5. RECIPIENTS AND CATEGORIES OF RECIPIENTS OF PERSONAL DATA

Personal data will be processed by the University's researchers and by other researchers involved in the project, who act on the basis of specific instructions on the purposes and means of the data processing. Moreover, personal data may also be processed by third parties who carry out tasks on the University's behalf in their capacity as 'data processors'. Their updated list is available at: <https://www.unive.it/pag/36643/>.

Aggregated and anonymous data (which means that you are no longer identifiable by it) may be shared with other Universities and/or research centres in order to carry out the activities of the research project and may be used for further research projects. It may also be included in publications, research reports, databases and quoted during classes, congresses and lectures.

The documents related to the research project (which may include your personal data) may be accessed by national and international bodies, by Italian and international journals committees in order to evaluate the lawfulness and fairness of the research conducted. Personal data may also be accessed by auditors.

Your personal data may be collected outside the EU/EEA during the research activities and later your personal data could be transferred from a non-EU country to the EU.

6. DATA SUBJECTS' RIGHTS AND HOW TO EXERCISE THEM

You have the right to obtain from the University, in the cases provided for by the Regulation, access to personal data, rectification, integration, their cancellation or processing limitation or to object to the data processing itself (articles 15 and following of the Regulation). . If the consent is the legal basis for the processing of personal data, you can withdraw your consent at any time without prejudice, writing to me or to the DPO at the below mentioned contact details. The University will stop the processing of your personal data unless there are compelling legitimate grounds to carry on with the processing. The request can be submitted, without any particular formal procedures, by contacting the Principal Investigator at roberta.raffaeta@unive.it and/or the Data Protection Officer directly at dpo@unive.it or by sending a communication to the following address: Ca' Foscari University Venice - Data Protection Officer, Dorsoduro 3246, 30123 Venice. Alternatively, you can contact the Data Controller, by writing a PEC (certified email) to protocollo@pec.unive.it.

Data subjects, who believe that the processing of their personal data is in violation of the provisions of the Regulation, have the right to file a complaint to the Data Protection Authority, as provided for by art. 77 of the Regulation itself, or to take appropriate legal action (Article 79 of the Regulation).

INFORMED CONSENT

The Undersigned,

born indate of birth

DECLARES

- To have read the Information sheet regarding the project ERC 'HealthXCross' (GA 949742);
• Its aims, risks and modalities have been illustrated clearly;
• I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and my questions have been answered to my satisfaction;
• I understand that my participation is voluntary, I can refuse to answer questions and I can withdraw from the study at any time, without giving any reason and without any consequence;
• I'm free to make a decision as to whether or not to participate in the research without any undue influence.

Having read, understood and accepted the above, I agree to participate in this research study.

.....

Place and date

Signature

Signature of the researcher

I also consent to being recontacted before the publication/presentation of research products (articles, books, slides, digital webpages/posts)

agree (email: ...) disagree

CONSENT TO THE PROCESSING OF SPECIAL CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA

I am aware that I can withdraw my consent at any time without prejudice. I have read the privacy notice above and I

agree disagree

to the processing of the above mentioned special categories of personal data, notably racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, for the purposes of the research project ERC.

Date, Place

Signature

RELEASE FORM FOR IMAGES AND AUDIO-VISUALS

Title of the Project: 949742 – HealthXCross – ERC Starting Grant (2021-2026)

I hereby declare that I allow Dr. Roberta Raffaetà, Principal Investigator of the project HealthXCross, to use the video-recordings and audio-recordings made of my own person, which constitute personal data pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 ("Regulation" and "Images"), to be stored and used as research material according to the conditions detailed below.

Subject to acquiring your consent pursuant to art. 96 et seq. of Italian Law no 633/1941, the Images shall be used for the sole purpose of documenting and promoting the activities carried out during the HealthXCross project and will be used in the reports, academic journal articles, books and book chapters, as well as during the seminars, workshop and conferences. Moreover, some material may be selected to be displayed on the project website and/or the project's social media. . The legal basis for this processing activity is represented by Art. 6.1.e) of the Regulation ("performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority").

Anyway, due to the fact that audio-visuials involve a higher probability that participants may be identified, we will follow up initial consent given by research participants with a reaffirmation by their viewing of the finished product, and by negotiations about ownership of and access to the recordings and conditions of publication.

Pictures and video will be taken by a mobile phone camera/videocamera or a dedicated camera/videocamera, stored in Cà Foscari University of Venice Google Drive and deleted from the camera/videocamera. These files will be destroyed within 5 years by the end of the project. This audiovisual data will help the Principal Investigator and team to develop analysis and to disseminate research insights. Some videos or pictures may be posted in the project's website and/or in the project's social media.

I also entitle the PI to post additional audiovisual material (photographs, sound recordings, videos in my possession and of which I own the copyrights) on the project's website for documentation purposes.

You may withdraw your consent at any time and request the removal of the Images by writing to the Data Protection Officer at dpo@unive.it. The University shall remove the Image from the project website or from social media within fifteen working days of receiving the request. Where the Images have been published in paper or multimedia format, in the event of your objection to further circulation, these Images shall be removed from the next reprinting.

The posing for, use, reproduction, publication and dissemination of the Images are understood to be free of charge. It is understood that, with this authorisation, the undersigned prohibits the use of his/her Image in contexts that may harm his/her personal dignity and decency.

As data subject, you have the right to obtain from the university, in the circumstances provided for by the Regulation, access to personal data, rectification, completion and erasure of said data or the restriction of processing, or the right to object to the processing (Articles 15 et seq. of the Regulation). The request can be made, without any formalities, by contacting the Data Protection Officer directly

Ca' Foscari
University
of Venice

Department of Philosophy
and Cultural Heritage

Department of Philosophy and Cultural Heritage
University Ca' Foscari Venice
Malcanton Marcorà – Dorsoduro 3484/D, 30123 Venice
P.IVA 00816350276 - CF 80007720271
www.unive.it/dip.fbc

at dpo@unive.it or by writing to the following address: Ca' Foscari University of Venice - Data Protection Officer, Dorsoduro 3246, 30123 Venice, Italy. Alternatively, you can contact the Data Controller by sending a certified email (PEC) to protocollo@pec.unive.it.

Data subjects who believe that the processing of personal data concerning them is undertaken in violation of the provisions of the Regulation also have the right to lodge a complaint with the Italian Data Protection Authority, as established by Art. 77 of the Regulation, or to an effective judicial remedy (Art. 79 of the Regulation).

I, the undersigned _____ born in
_____ on _____, having read
the disclaimer above, hereby

agree disagree

to the collection and use of my Images pursuant to Art. 96 et seq. of Italian Law no 633/1941 in the manner indicated in the preceding Privacy Statement.

(signature)

_____, _____
(place and date)

INFORMATION SHEET

Title of the Project: 949742 – HealthXCross – ERC Starting Grant (2021-2026)

What is the project about? Theme and expected impact of the project

My name is Roberta Raffaetà, and I am Associate Professor at Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Dept. of Philosophy and Cultural Heritage. I have received funding from the European Research Council (2021-2026) to analyse, with the help of other researchers part of my team, how scientists produce and coordinate knowledge within interdisciplinary platforms that compare and integrate data across time, space and species, and what are the impact of this research in terms of health concepts and practices. The project is for my own independent research and is not connected to any industry. By exploring how scientists advance science, it is possible to learn and foresee how society will change, and viceversa. The project, therefore, has the overall aim to strengthen the interaction between science and society through evaluation and communication. Your participation will also help to improve interdisciplinary research, education programs and policies.

What is involved with being a participant in the project? Methods of the project

Two main methods will involve research participants: 1) participant observation, 2) semi-structured interviews. Participant observation: a researcher will join a social situation (a meeting, lab work, etc...) observing it. During participant observation, the researcher may also make some video and take pictures. Semi-structured interviews: willing persons will be interviewed by the project's researcher. The researcher will propose a main theme (2-3 main questions) to be developed by the interviewee. The interview may last few minutes to hours, depending on the interviewee's willingness to elaborate and interact. Participation in interviews is entirely voluntary and arranged at a time and a place that suits the interviewee. The interviewee can skip questions who doesn't want to answer or can choose not to finish any part of the interview. In the context of this project, a research participant is defined as someone of whom we will collect personal data (ideas, pictures, audio-visuals) and gives consent to it. For example, labs or project consortiums include a number of people who will not be directly involved in the study and of whom we will not collect personal data. These will be considered 'third parties'.

Privacy and pseudonymization

Interviews: upon agreement, the interview will be taped to make sure that the researcher will not miss anything, but the interviewee's name won't be recorded in the interview transcript and kept separate from it, as indicated by art. 4(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679-General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The interviewees, therefore, cannot be identified from the name (unless otherwise agreed). Ethnographic interviews, however, are often saturated by personal information because they consist of those kinds of knowledge that determine social life. The processing of personal data may reveal ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health and data concerning a sex life or sexual orientation and therefore they may lead to indirect identification. For this reason, before to publish any paper/book that relates directly to some to research participant, we will share the manuscripts with her/him (if participants give the consent to it). They can withdraw consent for its use if feeling that anything that is written is causing discomfort or any potential threat.

Audio-visual data: due to the fact that these involve a higher probability that participants may be identified, we will follow up initial consent given by research participants with a reaffirmation of the consent for further disseminate it, and by negotiations about ownership of and access to the recordings and conditions of publication.

Participants can withdraw from participation in the project or parts of it if they change their mind later. This can be done by telephoning me or one of the research team members or putting this request in writing, for example in an email, without the need to give any reason. There are no consequences for withdrawing at any time. For participants who requested de-anonymization, the withdrawal of the consent has effect from the day of its request and it is *ex nunc*, not affecting the research products already published/presented.

Data access and archiving

No one but the researchers will have access to personal data such as interview recordings, fieldnotes, video, pictures, signed informed consent and pseudonyms conversion file. These will be stored in research team's computers, encrypted and protected by password, along with other IT measures to enhance data protection. The documents related to the research project (which may include your personal data) may be accessed by national and international bodies, by Italian and international journals committees in order to evaluate the lawfulness and fairness of the research conducted. Personal

data may also be accessed by auditors. Research data will be archived up to 5 yrs by the end of the project if there are personal data (except otherwise stipulated with the research participants themselves) and for non-personal data up to 20 years after the end of the project.

Third party policy

It is possible that the ethnography will include some non-working time and activities during which participants interact with third parties, but the focus will be on research participants and their relation to that third party – not the third party itself. I'll take all the precaution possible in any given situation to exclude third parties – especially children or others unable to consent - from the research interaction. No focused systematized data such as interviews or other will be collected about third parties.

Unexpected findings policy

Every ethnographic relationship resulting in reliable knowledge is built on mutual trust. However, in presence of unexpected findings such as illegal activities or findings of a sensitive nature with the potential to harm humanity, this trust can be overruled by values of a higher order.

Non-disclosure agreement

There is the possibility that some of the data gathered may be exceptionally sensitive, and akin to industrial intelligence. In relation to these kind of data, project's researchers will sign a non-disclosure agreement with the respective laboratories, to be negotiated before starting fieldwork. It will provide a clear definition of boundaries to preserve intellectual property and a basis for mutual trust and productive collaboration. For the data covered by the non-disclosure agreement, research participants will be enabled to claim their intellectual property at any time during data gathering and processing.

Data processing and sharing

Personal data such as interview recordings, fieldnotes, video, pictures, signed informed consent and pseudonyms conversion files will be accessible only by the University of Venice researcher who collected them within the HealthXCross project. Selected processed data may be used to write reports, academic journal articles, books and book chapters. The team will also present the results of the project at seminars, workshop and conferences and will display some selected and processed data on the website and associated social media.

Who can I contact for more information?

Please feel free to contact me at any time for more information. I would welcome any queries at any time. My contact details are below.

Thank you,

Roberta Raffaetà

P: 0039 3382846103

roberta.raffaeta@unive.it

PRIVACY NOTICE FOR RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS PROJECT ERC 'HealthXCross' (GA 949742)

in accordance with art. 13 of EU Regulation 2016/679 ("Regulation")

In this privacy notice, Ca' Foscari University of Venice ('University') will provide you with information on the collection of your personal data from the ERC HealthXCross (GA 949742) research project. For further information about the research project, see the Information Sheet above. If you have any question, please do not hesitate to contact the Principal Investigator by writing to the email address: roberta.raffaeta@unive.it

The research project has been developed in accordance with the sector's research standards and policies and it is stored at the Department of Philosophy and Cultural Heritage of Ca' Foscari University of Venice where it will be retained for 5 years after the conclusion of the research.

1. DATA CONTROLLER

The data controller is Ca' Foscari University of Venice, with headquarters in Dorsoduro n. 3246, 30123 Venice (VE), legally represented by the Rector.

2. DATA PROTECTION OFFICER

The University has appointed a "Data Protection Officer" ('DPO'), who can be contacted by writing to the email address: dpo@unive.it or to the following address: Ca' Foscari University, Venice, Data Protection Officer, Dorsoduro n. 3246, 30123 Venice (VE).

3. PERSONAL DATA CATEGORIES, PURPOSES AND LEGAL BASIS OF DATA PROCESSING

We will collect a range of personal data in order to carry out the research project activities. This may include personal data such as the participants' name, surname, contact details, experiences, emails, recorded interviews, pictures and videos. We may also collect, in certain situations, special categories of personal data, notably data related to racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health, data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation or data relating to criminal convictions and offences. We will collect this information in a variety of ways, such as through fieldnotes, audio and/or video recordings, interviews.

The processing of personal data will be carried out with the use of computerised procedures, adopting appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect it from unauthorised or illegal access, destruction, loss of integrity and confidentiality, even if accidental in nature.

In order to protect the confidentiality of the participants, the information collected will be de-identified, which means that all direct identifiers (such as name, surname, etc.) will be removed and replaced by a pseudonym instead. Therefore, the participants will no longer be directly identifiable from the data. The key for re-identification will be archived up to 5 yrs by the end of the project, then it will be irreversibly deleted.

The research activities are conducted by the University in the public interest as part of its official functions, therefore the legal basis for the processing of personal data is represented by art. 6.1.e) of the Regulation ("performance of a task carried out in the public interest").

With regards to the processing of special categories of personal data, the legal basis is represented by art. 9.2.a) of the Regulation ("explicit consent of the data subject") in connexion with art. 7.2 of "Regole deontologiche", Allegato A5 to D.Lgs. n. 196/2003. Therefore, at the end of this document, in case these data will be collected, we will ask for your consent to collect and process this type of personal data. You can withdraw your consent at any time without prejudice, writing to me or to the DPO at the contact details mentioned below. We will stop the processing of your personal data unless there are compelling legitimate grounds to carry on with the processing.

With regards to the usage of your email or your address and your name and surname in order to being recontacted before the publication/presentation of research products, the legal basis is represented by art. 6.1.a) of the GDPR ('consent'). You can withdraw your consent at any time without prejudice, writing to me or to the DPO at the above mentioned contact details.

With regards to the – eventually agreed - usage of your name and surname for the publications and other research products related to the research activities, such as interviews which have been conducted, the legal basis is represented by art. 6.1.a) of the GDPR ('consent'). You can withdraw your consent at any time without prejudice, writing to me or to the DPO at the above mentioned contact details. The withdrawal of the consent has effect from the day of its request and it is *ex nunc*, not affecting the research products already published/presented.

4. DATA RETENTION

Research data will be archived up to 5 yrs by the end of the project if there are personal data (except otherwise stipulated with the research participants themselves) and for non-personal data up to 20 years after the end of the project.

5. RECIPIENTS AND CATEGORIES OF RECIPIENTS OF PERSONAL DATA

Personal data will be processed by the University's researchers and by other researchers involved in the project, who act on the basis of specific instructions on the purposes and means of the data processing. Moreover, personal data may also be processed by third parties who carry out tasks on the University's behalf in their capacity as 'data processors'. Their updated list is available at: <https://www.unive.it/pag/36643/>.

Aggregated and anonymous data (which means that you are no longer identifiable by it) may be shared with other Universities and/or research centres in order to carry out the activities of the research project and may be used for further research projects. It may also be included in publications, research reports, databases and quoted during classes, congresses and lectures.

The documents related to the research project (which may include your personal data) may be accessed by national and international bodies, by Italian and international journals committees in order to evaluate the lawfulness and fairness of the research conducted. Personal data may also be accessed by auditors.

Your personal data may be collected outside the EU/EEA during the research activities and later your personal data could be transferred from a non-EU country to the EU.

6. DATA SUBJECTS' RIGHTS AND HOW TO EXERCISE THEM

You have the right to obtain from the University, in the cases provided for by the Regulation, access to personal data, rectification, integration, their cancellation or processing limitation or to object to the data processing itself (articles 15 and following of the Regulation). . If the consent is the legal basis for the processing of personal data, you can withdraw your consent at any time without prejudice, writing to me or to the DPO at the below mentioned contact details. The University will stop the processing of your personal data unless there are compelling legitimate grounds to carry on with the processing. The request can be submitted, without any particular formal procedures, by contacting the Principal Investigator at roberta.raffaeta@unive.it and/or the Data Protection Officer directly at dpo@unive.it or by sending a communication to the following address: Ca' Foscari University Venice - Data Protection Officer, Dorsoduro 3246, 30123 Venice. Alternatively, you can contact the Data Controller, by writing a PEC (certified email) to protocollo@pec.unive.it.

Data subjects, who believe that the processing of their personal data is in violation of the provisions of the Regulation, have the right to file a complaint to the Data Protection Authority, as provided for by art. 77 of the Regulation itself, or to take appropriate legal action (Article 79 of the Regulation).

CONSENT TO THE USE OF REAL NAMES

I (name, surname) _____

place of birth _____

date of birth _____

am aware that I can withdraw my consent at any time without prejudice. The withdrawal of the consent has effect from the day of its request and it is *ex nunc*, not affecting the research products already published/presented. I have read the privacy notice above and I

agree

disagree

to the use of my real name for the publications and other research products such as slides and digital webpages/posts related to the research activities under the ERC 'HealthXCross' (GA 949742) and with the means described in the Information sheet.

Date, Place _____

Signature _____